

Dexterity Outcomes For Grade 1 Disability In Leprosy Using Rood's Approach Versus Neural Tissue Mobilization

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ABSTRACT

Title: Dexterity Outcomes for Grade 1 Disability in Leprosy Using Rood's Approach Versus Neural Tissue Mobilization
Background: Leprosy is an infection affecting the peripheral nerves, may lead to disability in case proper treatment is not offered. Early diagnosis and treatment are important in leprosy. Physiotherapy plays an important role in the prevention of disability in leprosy.
Objective: The purpose of this study is to assess the dexterity results of grade 1 disability in leprosy cases via Rood's technique and neural tissue mobilization.
Methodology: The methodology employed an experiment on 36 individuals with leprosy and application of inclusion and exclusion criteria alongside the informed consent. These patients were randomly assigned into two different groups Group A and Group B. Group A was provided with treatments of quick icing, fast brushing, quick stretch and small joint compression as per the Rood's technique facilitation processes while group B underwent neural tissue mobilization involving nerve gliding exercises on ulnar, radial and median nerves of their upper extremities. All treatment occurred four times a week for four weeks. Measurements before and after intervention were taken via the Functional Dexterity Test (FDT) and Michigan Hand Outcomes Questionnaire (MHQ).
Result: Group A exhibited a high improvement level in relation to both FDT time as well as MHQ scores particularly for activities of daily living, pain, aesthetics and satisfaction levels.
Conclusion: The study shows Rood's approach facilitates better dexterity outcomes than neural tissue mobilization in leprosy patients with grade 1 disability.

Keywords: Rood's approach, neural tissue mobilization, dexterity, leprosy, disability, FDT, MHQ.

INTRODUCTION

Leprosy is an infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae* that affects the skin and peripheral nerves. The disease can lead to physical disabilities and deformities if not detected and treated early enough. According to WHO, the number of physical disabilities from leprosy should be reduced to fewer than one per million of the population through the use of effective ways of preventing and avoiding physical disabilities from the disease. This can be achieved through the early detection and treatment of leprosy patients who have features associated with physical disabilities ⁽¹⁾. Leprosy is a prevalent infectious condition that affects the peripheral nervous system and could lead to severe disabilities if not treated in good time. Therefore, early diagnosis and rapid treatment for nerve damage

are key considerations. The first symptom of leprosy is normally the damage of the cutaneous nerve endings, leading to loss of sensation to temperature stimuli and eventually affecting other sensations like pain and touch. In the late stages of the condition, sensations mediated by large nerve fibers can be compromised. Moreover, motor problems may emerge during the latter stage ⁽²⁾. On the national scale, the assessment of the program's effectiveness depends on the reports about grade-2 disabilities. Nevertheless, to prevent disability effectively, the evaluation of grade-1 disability should be prioritized. It is connected with the point that the impairment of nerves, either sensory or motor or both, normally happens before the deformation that characterizes grade-2 disability develops ⁽³⁾.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

As part of joint efforts with WHO, ILEP, and NLEP partners, the Central Leprosy Division has created the National Strategic Plan and Roadmap for Leprosy for the period of 2023-2027. In accordance with this roadmap, it is planned to stop the transmission of leprosy in India, complying with the WHO Roadmap for NTDs 2021-2030 and Global Strategy 2021-2030. The prevention strategy for disabilities related to leprosy includes three key components: early detection and proper treatment (MDT), prevention of disabilities related to leprosy (POD), and rehabilitation⁽⁴⁾. For complete rehabilitation, priority should first be given to restoring the physical disability that results from leprosy, and secondary consideration will include individualized adjustments of lifestyle modification for both the patient, his or her family, and the surrounding community⁽⁵⁾. The physical rehabilitation of the leprosy patients can be subdivided into the following main categories: 1. Assessment of nerve function impairment (NFI), 2. Impairment monitoring, and 3. Prevention of impairment deterioration⁽⁵⁾. Physiotherapy is indispensable for the multidisciplinary treatment of leprosy, where the physiotherapist makes notable contributions in the diagnosis, prevention, rehabilitation, and elimination of physical disabilities associated with leprosy⁽⁶⁾. There are many physiotherapy modalities, ranging from advanced neurophysiological modalities like the Rood method, to musculoskeletal approaches like neural mobilization, which have proven to be very useful in relieving pain, minimizing disabilities, and improving electromyography function of the impaired nerves⁽⁶⁻⁷⁾.

The disabilities of hands affect the performance of tasks of everyday life, and hence the need to conduct an evaluation of the improvement of hand dexterity as part of rehabilitation process in treating diseases becomes important. This research work seeks to assess the results of rehabilitation in patients with grade 1 disability of leprosy by comparison of Rood's technique and neural tissue mobilization.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Dr. D. Y. Patil Hospital & Research Institute, Kolhapur and Shenda Park Leprosy Hospital, Kolhapur. 36 patients were chosen

based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. All the patients were subjected to either Rood's approach technique or Neural tissue mobilization technique by using random sampling method. All the patients were under treatment for 4 weeks on 4 days a week after obtaining approval from the hospital ethical committee.

Inclusion criteria

The subjects for this study were patients suffering from leprosy and having Grade 1 disability. The subjects who had pain in their upper limbs measured by Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) were included in this study. Moreover, patients having sensory loss confirmed by sensory assessment tests were included. In addition, muscle weakness of the patient was evaluated by Manual Muscle Testing (MMT). Those patients whose muscle grades varied from 0 to 3 were selected. Moreover, those patients who took more than 55 seconds to finish the test of Functional Dexterity Test (FDT) were included in this study.

Exclusion criteria

Subjects with any kind of skin ulcers, blisters, or cuts on the hands were excluded from the study. Those with hand deformities like claw hand and digit shredding were also excluded. Also, patients with neuropathy due to other factors like diabetes, alcoholism, or cervical spondylitis were not included in the study. Subjects with low mental acuity levels affecting their performance in assessment were also excluded. Lastly, subjects who were lost to follow-ups from the Outpatient Department (OPD) were not included in the study. Subjects were divided into two groups using random sampling technique (Chit Method) in order to perform either of the Rood Technique or Neural Tissue Mobilization technique. The two techniques were compared by evaluating the subjects through Functional Dexterity Test and MHQ test. Procedure for the two groups was performed accordingly i.e., Rood's approach to group A and Neural Tissue Mobilization to group B. Subjects in the study had follow ups of 4 times a week for 4 weeks where exercise was applied. Outcome measures were obtained before and after 4 weeks of study period. All results were duly noted in

the Master chart. Analysis of Data was done in SPSS V28.

The patients in both groups were assessed using

1. Functional Dexterity Test
2. Michigan Hand function Questionnaire

These tests were conducted prior to the intervention and after 4 weeks of the intervention completion.

Functional dexterity test:

Figure: (i) 1st stage finger placement with 3 jaw chuck.

Figure: (ii) 2nd stage Turning the peg with 3 jaw chuck.

Figure: (iii) 3rd stage keeping the peg back in place.

The Michigan Hand Outcomes Questionnaire (MHQ)

The Michigan Hand Outcomes Questionnaire (MHQ) is a specific test used to determine the health outcomes of patients who are affected by chronic hand disorders. MHQ uses six different measures, which include (1) general hand ability, (2) activities of daily living (ADLs), (3) pain, (4) work ability, (5) appearance, and (6) satisfaction level about hand ability. MHQ also has a demographic part where patients provide their personal data such as gender and ethnicity. In all, there are 72 items in MHQ that take about 15 minutes to complete.

Reason for selection of Rood's approach:

Rood Approach is based on neurophysiology and involves the use of central nervous system reflexes. One of the basic principles of the Rood Approach is that motor patterns develop from primitive reflexes through the application of appropriate sensory stimulation of the correct sensory receptors in a normal sequential developmental pattern of enhancement of motor activity. The approach utilizes both facilitation and inhibition techniques and stresses that motor activity depends on sensory activity. Thus, facilitation techniques could be very useful in cases of sensory impairment, and inhibition techniques would reduce the sensitivity level, ultimately resulting in better motor activity⁽⁸⁾. The stimulation of the autonomic nervous system is another important component of the Rood approach. Depending on the intensity and the frequency of the stimulus, one or the other system gets activated. If the stimulus is quick and brief, then it evokes a strong synchronous motor reaction; and if the stimulus is fast but repetitive, then it causes a sustained reaction. In our study, facilitation techniques were used including various tactile and proprioceptive facilitative techniques. Among tactile techniques, for instance, icing techniques are useful for activation of the sympathetic nervous system, while light touch and fast brushing stimulate the parasympathetic nervous system⁽⁹⁾.

Application of Rood's approach

Tactile/exteroceptive facilitation

- The light stroking technique uses A delta sensory nerves, which are in turn associated with the fusimotor network of reciprocal innervations. This enables activation of low threshold hair end receptors and free nerve receptors that activate deep mobilizing muscles, increase corticosteroids in blood circulation, regulate fluid and electrolyte balance, and improve disease resistance. This technique involves application with the use of fingertips, soft brushes, or cotton applicators, and it is done at a rate of 3-5 strokes per session in 10 sessions, with 30 seconds between each session.
- Fast brushing stimulates the nerves of C fibers and is carried out in areas of the body representing the dermatomes of the same myotome. The effects of fast brushing last up to 30 minutes; it stimulates C fibers that branch out in multiple areas within the reflex arc. It is done by using a battery-powered brush, at 3 to 5 strokes per session, with 10 sessions in total, along with 30 seconds pause between each session.
- The process of Icing/ Thermal facilitation helps in achieving muscle activation as well as autonomic nervous system activation. Thermal facilitation includes two types: A icing, C icing, A-Icing. In A icing, the ice cubes are rapidly applied so as to elicit a reflex withdrawal similar to the light touch sensation. In C-icing, a high-threshold stimulus is produced by holding the ice cube for 15 to 20 minutes on the muscle belly or corresponding dermatome area. Both techniques of C-icing involve pressing of the ice cube on the body or applying quickly through icing, in which 3 strokes are taken with the ice cube, followed by blotting out the water droplets after each stroke, with 10 repetitions in all.

Proprioceptive facilitation

- Stretching of muscle which is intrinsic to body and has low threshold stimulus for the activation of a phasic response in the same muscle which was stretched. The effect of sudden stretch is instant in nature. It stimulates the proprioceptors and follows the law of reciprocal innervation, contributing to stability in the scapulothoracic area by supporting

more body weight on the ulnar side of the hand, hence increasing resistance by the hand.

- Compression of Joint leads to contraction of muscles that surround the joint. It can be done through manual compression or load bearing, for instance lying prone on the hands.

Reason for selection of Neural tissue mobilization:

There are mainly two types of neurodynamic tests: tensioning and sliding. Tensioning helps to generate compression on the nerve structure using body segment movement that results in increasing distances between the fixation points of the nerve structure. However, the purpose of sliding is to create movements alternatively around fixation points such that the nerve structure can move freely over its course. The significance of intraneural edema cannot be overlooked in peripheral nerve injuries since it makes the nerves vulnerable to compressive injuries. Hence, applying sliding tests in the acute stage might be beneficial.

Moreover, these techniques can be beneficial for reducing the increase in intraneural pressure that might compress nerve fibers and reduce the perfusion of the nerves, thereby causing ischemia and nerve conduction blockage. With regards to the chronic phase, especially when surgery has been done on the patient, the occurrence of intraneural fibrosis might cause dysfunction in the nerves. Here, tensioning techniques become extremely important because they help in slowly elongating Schwann cell bodies and internodes. Due to high intraneural pressure, the probability of axonal injury becomes more likely; thus, the signs need to be monitored while mobilizing the limb ⁽¹⁰⁾.

Nerve parenchyma degeneration, involving the perineurium, as well as the degeneration of the barrier function, is observed in the highly infiltrated fascicles. This occurs in leprosy cases with good CMI reactions. There is extensive damage to the nerves such that some fascicles are completely destroyed while others have minimal involvement and even appear to be relatively normal. There is also an observation of thick and convoluted myelin sheath associated with axonal degeneration together with increased numbers of small and thinly myelinated fibers, indicating

regeneration of the axon in the periphery of the granuloma ⁽¹⁰⁾.

Edema formation within the intraneural space plays an essential role in peripheral nerve injury, where nerves that are enlarged have shown greater sensitivity to compressive injuries. As such, the use of sliding techniques in the early stage might prove to be helpful due to nerve decompression and improved axoplasmic flow using oscillations. Mobilization sliding neurodynamic maneuvers were performed on the median, ulnar, and radial nerves for group B, conducted for 20 cycles during 3 sessions in a week, lasting for 4 weeks.

Application of Neural Tissue Mobilization

1. Median nerve sliding

Position of the patient includes lying supine on the treatment table with abduction of the shoulder at 90 degree angle and external rotation of the joint. The patient's forearm should be supinated, and his wrist remains in a neutral position together with the fingers being also supinated. Restraint is applied above the acromioclavicular joint inhibiting the process of elevation of the shoulder girdle at abduction. Additional restraint is also applied at the distal end of the arm. This procedure requires subjects to lie supine on the table, and their scapula is not touching the table. In addition, maintaining depression of the shoulder girdle, the following joint movements should be executed: extension, abduction, and lateral rotation of the glenohumeral joint; elbow's extension; forearm's supination; and extension of wrist, fingers, and thumb. Neural mobilization is achieved through oscillatory techniques involving slow rhythmical oscillations of wrist flexion and extension and performed with 20 oscillations per minute and repeated 3 times. For sliding techniques both the elbow and cervical joints move in the same direction. Thus, if the right elbow is flexed, then the lateral cervical flexion is moved to the left side.

2. Ulnar nerve sliding

The patient adopts a comfortable stance. Guidance by verbal and tactile cues is provided by the therapist. The process includes the following steps: 1. The arm should be flexed forward, the elbow stretched out, the

wrist, and fingers flexed; gradually stretch the wrist and fingers while ensuring that the elbow is kept straight. Then flex the elbow while the wrist and fingers remain stretched. 2. Secondly, the arm should be placed in an abducted position (away from the body), the wrist should be flexed, the arm should be externally rotated, and the neck should be laterally flexed to the opposite side. Finally, perform neural mobilization using oscillations of wrist flexion and extension slowly and rhythmically. Perform 20 oscillations per minute repeated three times, with a break of one minute after each trial.

3. Radial nerve sliding

The client is placed in a comfortable position. The movement is guided by the therapist verbally or manually. This exercise requires depression of the shoulder, wrist flexion, internal rotation of the wrist, inclusion of lateral and cervical flexion, and wrist flexion when the shoulder is extended. After this positioning, the nerve mobilization is done through rhythmic oscillations of wrist flexion and extension. The number of oscillations to be done is 20 per minute and this process is carried out thrice within the same period, taking a one-minute break after each session. It is required to stop when one feels stretching and not pain ⁽¹¹⁻¹²⁾.

Basic grip strengthening exercises

Alongside the use of Rood's Approach Technique and the Neural Tissue Mobilization technique, various basic exercises to strengthen the hands are practiced. They have been standardized for both technique groups A and B. Ball squeeze exercises

The strength of grip is defined as the force with which muscles in our hands press or grab things we use in our daily life when opening boxes, carrying shopping, and using keyboards. One of the best ways to improve the strength and function of our hands is Hand Ball Therapy. Fine motor skills refer to the ability to move our hands in detail when carrying out some specific actions such as writing, dressing ourselves, or playing an instrument. Hand Ball Therapy helps us improve these skills as it is essential to move and manipulate the ball to do so. Exercises involving squeezing and manipulating a ball will activate and train muscles and joints that control the fine motor skills. Such activities

will help increase the strength and coordination of fingers and hands. Patients are expected to do 10-15 squeezes of the ball with three repetitions ⁽¹³⁾.

Follow-up of participants:

Often, leprosy has posed a significant economic burden for the patients and their relatives. The systemic symptoms that accompany this health problem reduce the income of the people involved, and increase expenses required for medical care. Families with limited finances are more vulnerable to sinking into poverty, which eventually causes poor immunity in the end. Leprosy is considered a socio-economic disease because lack of education causes limited employment chances; this, together with poverty, results in reduced immunity because of poor nutrition and hygiene. However, the contribution of family members plays an important role in shaping the behavior towards healthcare, since they help to shape the patient's attitudes by serving as moderators that facilitate financial, professional and other kinds of support such as symptom recognition and health education, among others ⁽¹⁴⁾.

Contact with the patients:

The patients were set to receive follow-ups four days a week for four weeks. There existed a communication barrier during the follow-up meetings. It was very difficult for the researcher to contact the patients regarding their follow-up appointments. Because of the social stigma of the illness, it was not possible for the researcher to contact any member of the family for follow-up appointments. The researcher could communicate directly with the patient and request a follow-up visit only.

Counselling for missed visits:

In case of some patients, going for these treatment sessions meant stopping any income generation process. The patients were constantly receiving reconciliations in order not to drop out during treatment. Considering that many patients coming from poor economic backgrounds were enrolled, free checks, consultations, and treatment sessions were made available. In order to motivate patients to come back, some were given daily allowances.

Dropout after missed visit:

For all the participants, there were 4 days per week treatment schedule that continued for 4 weeks, which made a total of 16 treatment sessions. Participants who attended the clinic for a minimum of 12 treatment sessions were only included in the study. The participants who came to the clinic less than 12 times were dropped from the study.

Data Collection:

Data was collected from all participants using the prepared Clinical Record Form.

Neurological examination were done by motor examination and sensory examination.

In motor examination onset of symptoms were assessed for sudden/acute, gradual/progressive.

Severity of pain was assessed using numeric pain rating scale on a 1 to 10-level.

Muscle weakness was tested using manual muscle testing and recorded.

MMT grades

Grade 0- No movement

Grade 1- Flicker of contraction

Grade 2- Full range of motion with elimination of gravity

Grade 3- Full range of motion against gravity

Grade 4- Full range of motion against gravity with minimal resistance

Grade 5- Full range of motion against gravity with maximum resistance

Range of motion for all upper limb joints were assessed by using goniometer and degrees were documented.

Sensory assessment was done using slandered sensory assessment Scale for exteroceptive, proprioceptive and combine cortical sensations and recorded.

Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	Grade 4
Normal/Present /Intact	Impaired / Inaccurate	Delayed response	Exaggerated response	Absent

Pre and post assessment of Outcome measures were taken.

Pre and post assessment with Functional Dexterity Test.

Pre and post assessment of Michigan Hand Function Questionnaire.

Data Analysis:

Outcome measures were recorded pre and post study after 4 weeks. All data was entered in the Master Chart. Data was analyzed using SPSS V28 software. Data was analyzed using pair-t test within the group

for two outcome measures and by using unpaired -t test between the groups. All results were represented in tabular format and graphical manner.

RESULT:

Study Population

Total 36 patients with Grade 1 Leprosy as per inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled in the study.

During follow-up of 4 weeks, as per methodology, 7 participants were lost to follow up.

Table (i) Drop out of patients

Group	Enrolled	Drop-out	Completed
A	22	4	18
B	21	3	18

Age Distribution

Mean age of all participants in study was between 47 – 51 years.

Table (ii) Age distribution

Group	Mean Age(Years)
A	50.61
B	48.11

Gender Distribution

Due to the randomization method employed for patient selection, there were no fixed criteria for including patients in specific groups. Upon analysis, it was determined that in Rood's approach technique, designated as group A, there were 7 males and 11 females included. In the Neural Tissue Mobilization

technique, referred to as group B, 10 males and 8 females were included.

Table (iii) Gender distribution

Gender	Roods		NTM	
	No of Patients	Percentage	No of Patients	Percentage
Male	7	38.89%	10	55.56%
Female	11	61.11%	8	44.44%
Total	18	100.00%	18	100.00%

Hand Dominance:

Majority of participants were right-dominant with nearly equal participants in both groups being left-handed.

Table (i) Hand dominance

Hand Dominance	Roods (A)		NTM(B)	
	No of Patients	Percentage	No of Patients	Percentage
Right	16	88.89%	15	83.33%
Left	2	11.11%	3	16.67%
Total	18	100.00%	18	100.00%

In Both the groups A and B almost all participants, affected limb was the dominant hand. Some participants had complaint about the bi-lateral hands involvement but the severity of symptoms were more for dominant hand.

Table (ii) Group A Hand dominance versus hand involvement

Group A (n=18)	Affected Right	Affected Left	Dominant affected
Right Dominance (n=16)	16	0	100%
Left Dominance (n= 2)	2	0	100%

Table (iii) Group B Hand dominance versus hand involvement

Group B (n=18)	Right involved	Left involved	Dominant affected
Right Dominance (n=15)	15	0	100%
Left Dominance (n= 3)	3	0	100%

Grade I Leprosy findings**A) Analysis of sensory assessment**

Sensory assessment to categorize the patient as Grade I leprosy was done using the standard Sensory Assessment Grading Scale.

Table (i) Analysis of Exteroceptive sensations.

Exteroceptive sensations grades(0-4)	Touch		Pain		Temperature		Pressure	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
0	4	11.11%	3	8.33%	0	0.00%	5	13.89%
1	21	58.33%	19	52.78%	16	44.44%	15	41.67%
2	11	30.56%	14	38.89%	20	55.56%	16	44.44%
3	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
4	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Total	36	100.00%	36	100.00%	36	100.00%	36	100.00%

Assessment of Exteroceptive sensations revealed that majority of participants demonstrated Grade 1 or Grade 2 deficit of Touch, Pain, Pressure and Temperature. All participants demonstrated abnormalities of Temperature perception.

Table (ii) Analysis of Proprioceptive sensations.

Proprioceptive sensations grades	JPS		VIS		DPP	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
0	21	58.33%	16	44.44%	20	55.56%
1	4	11.11%	8	22.22%	6	16.67%
2	11	30.56%	12	33.33%	10	27.78%
3	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
4	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Total	36	100.00%	36	100.00%	36	100.00%

Assessment of Proprioceptive sensations revealed that majority of participants demonstrated Grade 0, Grade 1 or Grade 2 deficit of joint position sense, vibration sense, deep pressure pain.

Table (iii) Analysis of combine cortical sensations.

Combine cortical sensation grades (0-4)	STRG		BARO		GRAP		TDP		TAL	
	Frequency	Percentage								
0	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	9	25.00%
1	14	38.89%	14	38.89%	16	44.44%	18	50.00%	10	27.78%
2	22	61.11%	22	61.11%	20	55.56%	18	50.00%	17	47.22%

3	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
4	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Total	36	100.00%	36	100.00%	36	100.00%	36	100.00%	36	100.00%

Assessment of combine cortical sensations revealed that majority of participants demonstrated Grade 1 or Grade 2 deficit of stereognosis, barognosis, graphesthesia, two-point discrimination and tactile localization.

B) Analysis of manual muscle strength

All patients in Group A, who underwent Rood's approach, and Group B, who received neural tissue mobilization, were evaluated using manual muscle

testing. The patients were classified based on muscle strength as either having decreased muscle strength or normal muscle strength. Out of 36 patients, all were found to have decreased muscle strength.

Table (iv) Analysis of manual muscle strength.

MMT	Roods		NTM	
	No of Patients	Percentage	No of Patients	Percentage
Decreased	18	100.00%	18	100.00%
Normal	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Total	18	100.00%	18	100.00%

C) Analysis of joint range of motion

All patients in Group A, who underwent Rood's approach, and Group B, who received neural tissue mobilization, were evaluated based on the joint range of motion of the affected hand. Patients were

classified into two categories: those with decreased joint range of motion (ROM) and those with normal ROM. In Group A, consisting of 18 patients, 10 exhibited decreased ROM while 8 had normal ROM. In Group B, also comprising 18 patients, 14 were identified with decreased ROM and 4 maintained a normal range of motion in the affected upper limb.

Table (v) Analysis of Range of motion in affected upper limb

Joint ROM	Roods		NTM	
	No of Patients	Percentage	No of Patients	Percentage
Decreased	10	55.55%	14	77.77%
Normal	8	44.44%	4	22.22%
Total	18	100.00%	18	100.00%

Outcome Measures

Quantitative measures for ADL analysis

Functional Dexterity Test (FDT), on the other hand, was created to measure the functional dexterity of the participant within the least time possible while still giving important information about the participant's functional abilities in performing tasks using 3-jaw

chuck prehensions by fingers and thumb. It is essential to evaluate the functional dexterity of the hands since it helps in understanding the ability of individuals in carrying out simple activities that need 3-jaw chuck prehensions like buttoning shirts, tying shoelaces, fastening nuts and bolts, as well as lacing yarn. The patient is asked to continue turning the pegs using the new peg without starting a new trial, and the timer continues where it stopped. The following two times are measured: (1) the first time in seconds taken

to finish the task, and (2) the total time including penalties to the first time. The total time plus the penalty is considered the final score and is used in evaluating the functional level of the participant. From a statistical viewpoint, the level of measurement is considered interval, and parametric statistics are applied in research.

Pre –Pre Comparison of FDT for Group A and Group B

Values of time taken to complete the FDT in pre test for both group A and group B were compared. P-Value is 0.016 ($P < 0.05$) shows that the both groups were comparable.

Table Pre –Pre Comparison of FDT for Group A and Group B

Group	FDT Test	Mean (Sec)	P- Value
Group A	Pre test	224.44	0.016
Group B	Pre Test	260.56	

Table Pre –Post Comparison of FDT for Group A

Rood's	Time-Point	Mean (Sec)	S.D.	P-value
FDT	Pre	224.44	46.71	0.0000000068497
	Post	158.17	39.37	
	Change in time taken	66.27 Sec.		

Figure Pre –Post Comparison of FDT for Group A

Pre –Post Comparison of FDT for Group A Rood's approach

(By using paired t-test)

The overall score, calculated as the sum of total time and penalties by using paired t-test, for the pre-FDT using Rood's approach had a mean of 224.44 seconds and a standard deviation of 46.71. In contrast, the post-FDT mean was 158.17 seconds with a standard deviation of 39.37. The p-value for the pre-post comparison of FDT in Group A using Rood's approach was 0.0000000068497, indicating that Rood's technique was significantly effective in enhancing functional dexterity for this group.

Pre –Post Comparison of FDT for Group B Neural tissue mobilization

(By using paired t-test)

The overall score, calculated as the sum of total time and penalties by using paired t-test, for the pre-FDT using Neural tissue mobilization had a mean of 260.56

seconds and a standard deviation of 38.64. In contrast, the post-FDT mean was 228.72 seconds with a standard deviation of 39.58. The p-value for the pre-post comparison of FDT in Group B using Neural tissue mobilization was 0.0000022414, indicating that neural tissue mobilization technique was effective in enhancing functional dexterity for this group.

Table Pre –Post Comparison of FDT for Group B

NTM	Time-Point	Mean (Sec)	S.D.	P-value
FDT	Pre	260.56	38.64	0.0000022414
	Post	228.72	39.58	
	Change in time taken	31.84 Sec		

Figure Pre –Post Comparison of FDT for Group B

Group-wise Comparison

(By using unpaired t-test)

The overall score, derived from the total time and penalties using an unpaired t-test, was assessed for the post-FDT employing Rood's approach for group A and Neural tissue mobilization for group B. The mean time for group A utilizing Rood's approach was 158.17 seconds and standard deviation of 39.37 with change in percentage 29.25%. In comparison, group B's post-FDT mean for Neural tissue mobilization was 228.72 seconds, accompanied by a standard deviation of 39.58 and change in percentage 12.21%. The p-value obtained from the unpaired t-test for the

The analysis of FDT indicated that the application of Rood's approach technique in group A was significantly more effective than the application of Neural tissue mobilization technique in group B in enhancing the functional dexterity of the patients. Group A participants took significantly lesser time for completion of FDT than Group B at the end of 4 week interventions as compared to the start.

Comparison between both groups was 0.0000029116.

Table Group wise comparison of FDT

Outcome	Group	Mean	S.D.	Percent change	P-value
FDT	Rood's Group A	158.17	39.37	29.25%	0.0000029116
	NTM Group B	228.72	39.58	12.21%	

Figure Group wise comparison of FDT

Qualitative and quantitative measures for ADL, pain, aesthetics and satisfaction analysis

The Michigan Hand Outcomes Questionnaire (MHQ) is a specialized qualitative and quantitative tool created to assess health outcomes in individuals with chronic hand conditions. It features six unique domains: (1) overall hand function, (2) activities of daily living (ADLs), (3) pain, (4) work performance, (5) aesthetics, and (6) patient satisfaction concerning hand function. Furthermore, it contains a demographic section that collects data on patients' gender, ethnic background, and other pertinent factors. The MHQ consists of 72 questions and generally takes approximately 15 minutes to complete, whether self-administered or conducted by an investigator. This questionnaire can be employed to evaluate a patient's overall hand function or, when administered at multiple intervals (such as pre- and post-treatment), to monitor changes in hand function over time .

Pre –Pre Comparison of MHQ for Group A and Group B

Values of time taken to complete the MHQ in pre test for both group A and group B were compared. P-Value is 0.026 ($P < 0.05$) shows that the both groups were comparable.

Table Pre –Pre Comparison of FDT for Group A and Group B

Group	MHQ Score	Mean score	P- Value
Group A	Pre test	23.31	0.026
Group B	Pre Test	17.74	

Pre –Post Comparison of MHQ for Group A Rood’s approach

(By using paired t-test)

The overall score, calculated as the sum of all 6 domains using paired t-test, for the pre-MHQ using Rood's approach had a mean of 23.31 and a standard

deviation of 7.68. In contrast, the post-MHQ mean was 44.24 with a standard deviation of 7.78. The p-value for the pre-post comparison of MHQ in Group A using Rood's approach was 0.000000000012190,

indicating that Rood's technique was significantly effective in optimizing ADLs, pain, aesthetics and satisfaction for this group.

Table Pre –Post Comparison of MHQ for Group A

Rood's Approach	Time-Point	Mean	S.D.	P-value
MHQ score	Pre	23.31	7.68	0.000000000012190
	Post	44.24	7.78	
	Change in Score	20.93		

Figure Pre –Post Comparison of MHQ for Group A

Pre –Post Comparison of MHQ for Group B Neural tissue mobilization

(By using paired t-test)

The overall score, calculated as the sum of all 6 domains using paired t-test, for the pre-MHQ using Neural tissue mobilization technique had a mean of

17.74 and a standard deviation of 5.19. In contrast, the post-MHQ mean was 23.45 with a standard deviation of 6.63. The p-value for the pre-post comparison of MHQ in Group B using Neural tissue mobilization technique was 0.0000081121, indicating that Neural tissue mobilization technique was effective in optimizing ADLs, pain, aesthetics and satisfaction for this group.

Table Pre –Post Comparison of MHQ for Group B

NTM	Time-Point	Mean	S.D.	P-value
MHQ score	Pre	17.74	5.19	0.0000081121
	Post	23.45	6.63	
	Change in score	5.71		

Figure Pre –Post Comparison of MHQ for Group B

Group-wise Comparison

(By using unpaired t-test)

The overall score, derived from the total calculations of all 6 domains of MHQ questionnaire using an unpaired t-test, was assessed for the post-MHQ employing Rood's approach for group A and Neural tissue mobilization for group B. The mean value for group A utilizing Rood's approach was 44.24 with a standard deviation of 7.78. In comparison, group B's post-MHQ mean value for Neural tissue mobilization was 23.45, accompanied by a standard deviation of

6.63. The p-value obtained from the unpaired t-test for the comparison between both groups was 0.00000000022124. The analysis of MHQ questionnaire indicated that the application of Rood's approach technique in group A was significantly more effective than the application of Neural tissue mobilization technique in group B in optimizing ADLs, pain, aesthetics and satisfaction.

MHQ score of Group A participants is significantly improved than Group B at the end of 4 week interventions as compared to the start.

Table Group wise comparison of MHQ

Outcome	Group	Mean	S.D.	Change in Percentage	P-value
MHQ score	Rood's Group A	44.24	7.78	47.53%	0.00000000022124
	NTM Group B	23.45	6.63	24.34%	

Figure Group wise comparison of MHQ

Post Intervention outcome comparison

The purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of Rood's technique, which is an advanced neuro physiotherapy technique, compared to neural tissue mobilization, an advanced musculoskeletal manual physiotherapy technique, on the dexterity of individuals with grade 1 leprosy. Thirty-six subjects were recruited from the study sample population after meeting certain inclusion and exclusion criteria, and they gave informed consent. The subjects were then subdivided into two equal groups of eighteen each, where Group A received therapy using the Rood technique, while Group B received neural tissue mobilization therapy, by adopting random selection techniques. Before administering therapy to the two groups, their levels of dexterity were assessed using the Functional Dexterity Test (FDT) and the Michigan Hand Outcome Questionnaire (MHQ). After the

administration of the therapy, the two groups were then retested using FDT and MHQ, respectively, and the data were appropriately recorded. Statistical tests that were applied in analyzing the data included a paired t-test of one outcome between the two treatment groups and unpaired t-tests for two outcomes in each group.

Post intervention outcomes Comparison of group A Rood's approach

(Paired t-test used)

The pre and post-analysis of the outcomes for FDT and MHQ conducted for group A indicates a p-value of less than 0.05, demonstrating that Rood's approach technique significantly enhances the optimization of activities of daily living (ADLs), alleviates pain, improves aesthetics, and increases patient satisfaction.

Table Post intervention outcomes Comparison of group A

Rood's	Time-Point	Mean	S.D.	Change in Percentage	P-value
FDT	Post	158.17	39.37	29.25%	0.000000000 68497
MHQ score	Post	44.24	7.78	47.53%	0.000000000 012190

Post intervention outcomes Comparison of group B Neural tissue mobilization

(paired t-test used)

The pre and post-analysis of the outcomes of FDT and MHQ conducted for group B indicates a p-value

of less than 0.05, demonstrating that neural tissue mobilization technique moderately enhances the optimization of activities of daily living (ADLs), alleviates pain, improves aesthetics, and increases patient satisfaction.

Table Post intervention outcomes Comparison of group B

NTM	Time-Point	Mean	S.D.	Change in Percentage	P-value
FDT	Post	228.72	39.58	12.21%	0.000022414
MHQ score	Post	23.45	6.63	24.34%	0.000081121

Post intervention outcomes Comparison of group A versus group B

(Unpaired t-test used)

Table Post intervention outcomes Comparison of Group A versus group B

Outcome	Group	Mean	S.D.	Change in Percentage	P-value
FDT	Rood's (A)	158.17	39.37	29.25%	0.0000029116
	NTM (B)	228.72	39.58	12.21%	
MHQ score	Rood's (A)	44.24	7.78	47.53%	0.0000000022124
	NTM (B)	23.45	6.63	24.34%	

Result in summery

According to the results of the analysis of the data collected after the experiment, it became evident that the application of Rood's approach by Group A led to a substantial reduction in time spent on completing the functional dexterity test when compared to neural tissue mobilization by the Group B patients. Moreover, the evaluation of MHQ scores showed a substantial positive impact of Rood's approach on the optimization of ADLs, pain, aesthetic appearance, and general satisfaction levels when compared to the scores of the patients from Group B who received neural tissue mobilization. In conclusion, the results showed that Rood's approach proved to be much more efficient in optimizing ADLs, relieving patients from pain, improving their aesthetic appearances, and increasing their general satisfaction levels. Thus, it can be claimed that Rood's approach was more effective than neural tissue mobilization in improving dexterity outcomes among patients with grade 1 disability caused by leprosy.

DISCUSSION:

In regard to the national level, the evaluation of program efficiency is done strictly on the basis of grade-2 disabilities only. Nevertheless, when it comes to disability prevention, grade-1 evaluation is crucial. It is so because the dysfunction of nerve tissue may occur either sensory or motor, even prior to the emergence of deformities classified as grade-2. Consequently, the individuals diagnosed with grade-2 disabilities had to have experienced grade-1 disabilities beforehand. Thus, it can be stated that when examining any case of leprosy, the examination of the peripheral nerves, including sensory nerve function impairment, motor nerve function impairment, and palpation of the nerves to identify thickening, tenderness, and reaction to grade-1

disabilities (20), is indispensable in addition to the examination of skin lesions. Our research indicates that the examination of grade-1 leprosy was vital to accomplish the objectives outlined in the Global Leprosy Strategy by WHO.

Effect of sensory stimulus on motor performance

Rood proposed through his observations in the clinic that sensory stimulation can be used to bring about motor activity that comes from the cortex. This is because voluntary activity, repeated actions, or practice can help develop motor activities necessary in addressing the problems brought about by the cortical lesion. The basis for the theory put forward by Rood is that the stimulation of the autonomic nervous system not only helps bring about motor activities of vital organs but can also influence the somatosensory system and the sensorimotor integration. The neurophysiological theory by Rood shows that there is need to study some physiological aspects that have not been sufficiently addressed in the past ⁽²¹⁾.

In our review of the experiment, we found that the use of the neurophysiotherapy strategy, especially the Rood therapy strategy with facilitation, has been very useful in improving activities of daily living, decreasing pain, improving aesthetics, and increasing overall satisfaction in grade 1 leprosy patients. Leprosy was believed to affect only the peripheral nerves and not the brain; however, through this research, it has become clear that brain plasticity is also possible after nerve injury or damage.

Effect of Rood's approach on Neuroplasticity

Destruction of the peripheral nerves as a consequence of leprosy is capable of bringing about certain changes in the brain ⁽²²⁾. The findings indicate that the brain map corresponding to a particular muscle can be

altered; hence, not only does leprosy cause peripheral nerve destruction, but it provides evidence in support of brain plasticity. Peripheral neuropathies are brought about by various factors, and although the current therapeutic procedures target their causes, there is still much difficulty in repairing damaged nerve fibers. This brings to the fore the possibility of utilizing the theory of brain plasticity in therapy. It has also been noted that brain-derived neurotrophic factor acts as an important mediator during motor learning, and its release in activity-dependent manners is critical for creating plasticity of the brain as a response to experience.

Study limitations

However, although there were a lot of good points of the study, there were some limitations too. First of all, the sample size was quite low for grade 1 leprosy patients. Hence, randomized trials with more samples should be conducted in order to examine how much both physiotherapeutic methods such as Rood technique and Neural Tissue Mobilization help patients in performing daily routines better, reducing pain, achieving aesthetic looks, and being satisfied. Besides, there could not be enough time in following up on the protocols. Moreover, the sample was taken only from one district, so the results may not be precise because of the lack of diversification. Also, there are very few scientific publications that consider advanced methods of treatment of grade 1 leprosy patients.

CONCLUSION:

From an analysis of the data collected after intervention, it appears that the Rood's method employed by Group A played a significant role in reducing the time required to complete the task of functional dexterity when compared to neural tissue mobilization used by Group B patients. Additionally, it is evident from the analysis of the MHQ scores that patients from Group A who were treated using the Rood's method experienced a dramatic increase in their MHQ scores related to ADL improvement, pain control, aesthetics, and general satisfaction when compared to Group B patients. Finally, it can be concluded that Rood's method employed in neurophysiotherapy is far much more effective than other methods in ensuring proper ADL

improvement, pain reduction, aesthetics, and general patient satisfaction. Thus, the study proves that the Rood's technique is better than others in improving dexterity outcomes in leprosy patients with grade 1 disability.

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REFERENCES

1. Hidyana L. de Paula, RN, Carlos D. F. de Souza, Sara R. Silva, RN, Paulo R. S. Martins Filho, Josafá G. Barreto; Ricardo Q. Gurgel, Luis E. Cuevas, MTropMed, Victor S. Santos, Risk Factors for Physical Disability in Patients With Leprosy A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis JAMA Dermatol. 2019;155(10):1120-1128.
2. Joy Vijayan, Einar P.W- Smith. The international textbook of leprosy. Chapter 2.5. Neurological Manifestation of leprosy. 1-20.
3. Jhuma Sarkar, Aparajita Dasgupta, Debashis Dutt. Disability among new leprosy patients, an issue of concern: An institution based study in an endemic district for leprosy in the state of West Bengal, India. Indian Journal of Dermatology, Venereology, and Leprology. 2012; 78(3):328-334.
4. National Strategic Plan and Road-map for Leprosy. National Leprosy Eradication Programme 2023-2027.
5. M Sathish Kumar P, David P Kumar, Karthikeyan G. The International textbook of leprosy. Chapter 4.3. Physical rehabilitation in leprosy. 1-43.
6. Vandana Yadav, Charu Gera, Ravinder Yadav. Evolution in Hemiplegic Management: A Review. International Journal of Health Sciences and Research. 2018; 8(5): 360-369.
7. Dinora S Santi Bonazza, Vanessa Matias Souza Duarte, Thiago da Rosa Lima, Ciro Martins Gomes, Treatment of neuropathic pain in leprosy patients with a physiotherapeutic protocol combined with photobiomodulation. Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso. 2024;10(18):1-16.

8. Dr. Maithili Samrat Patil. Effect of Roods Approach on Dexterity of Hand for Grade 1 Disability in Leprosy. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*.2023; 5(5):1-12
9. Kuki Bordoloi, Rup Sekhar Deka. Scientific Reconciliation of the Concepts and Principles of Rood Approach. *International Journal of Health Sciences & Research*.2018; 8(9):225-234.
10. Herman Henrique Silva Santana, Iasmyn Adélia Victor Fernandes de Oliveira, Êmyle Martins Lima, Alena Ribeiro Alves Peixoto Medrado, Katia Nunes, Ana Maria Blanco Martinez, Abrahão Fontes Baptista. Neurodynamic Mobilization and Peripheral Nerve Regeneration: A Narrative Review. *International Journal of Neuro rehabilitation*.2015; 2(2):163-168.
11. Larissa Sales Téles Véras, Rodrigo Gomes de Souza Vale, Danielli Braga de Mello. Electromyography function, disability degree, and pain in leprosy patients undergoing neural mobilization treatment. *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical* 2012; 45(1):83-88.
12. Dr. Dabholkar Tejashree, Dabholkar Ajit S. The Effect of Nervous Tissue Mobilization on Pinch & Grip Strength. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*2014; 7(3):251-253.
13. Jose Manuel Pérez-Mármol, Ma Carmen García-Ríos, Effectiveness of a fine motor skills rehabilitation program on upper limb disability, manual dexterity, pinch strength, range of fingers motion, performance in activities of daily living, functional independency, and general self-efficacy in hand osteoarthritis: A randomized clinical trial. *Journal of Hand Therapy*.2017; 30(3):262-273.
14. Annisa Ika Putril, Ruth M. H. Peters, Kevin De Sabbata. A socio-ecological model of the management of leprosy reactions in Indonesia and India using the experiences of affected individuals, family members and healthcare providers. *Putri et al. BMC Health Services Research* (2025);25 (196):1-19.
15. Kevin K. Chui, Shen-che Yan, Thomas J Schmitz. Examination of sensory functions. *Textbook of Physical Rehabilitation* by Susan B. O'Sullivan. 73-108.
16. Susan B. O'Sullivan, Richard J Mckibben. Examination of motor functions, motor control and motor learning. *Textbook of Physical Rehabilitation* by Susan B. O'Sullivan. 135-187.
17. Aaron, DH, Stegink CW. Development of the Functional Dexterity Test (FDT). *J Hand Ther*.2003; 16: 12-21.
18. With permission from University of Michigan, purchase letter dated 13th October 2023.
19. Mari'a Visitación Martínez-Fernández, Irene Sandoval Hernandez, Jesús Martínez-Cal, Carmen Sarabia-Cobo. Cross-cultural evaluation of the Michigan Hand Outcomes Questionnaire: a systematic review. *Hand Surgery and Rehabilitation*.2024; 43:1-16.
20. Jhuma Sarkar, Aparajita Dasgupta, Debashis Dutt. Disability among new leprosy patients, an issue of concern: An institution based study in an endemic district for leprosy in the state of West Bengal, India. *Indian Journal of Dermatology, Venereology, and Leprology*. 2012; 78(3):328-334.
21. Kuki Bordoloi, Rup Sekhar Deka. Scientific Reconciliation of the Concepts and Principles of Rood Approach. *International Journal of Health Sciences & Research*.2018; 8(9):225-234.
22. Dorit H Aaron, Caroline W Stegink Jansen. Development of the Functional Dexterity Test (FDT): construction, validity, reliability, and normative data. *Journal of hand therapy*.2003;16(1):12-21.

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